

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS OF TEACHING SPECIALTY SUBJECTS IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: the existing progress in the field of science, technology, production and technology determines the image of modern society. The most important characteristic feature of modern society is that globalization is noticeable in all its spheres. Globalization itself requires rapid movement, immediate receipt of the necessary information, its processing and effective application in practice. Thus, only those personnel who are well versed in their field, have a high level of professional qualifications, have a wealth of experience and skills. Therefore, in the process of training personnel in higher educational institutions, it is advisable to take into account this requirement of the period.

Keywords: education, innovation, learning efficiency, foreign language, grammar, pedagogical skills.

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ ДИСЦИПЛИН В СИСТЕМЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: существующий прогресс в области науки, техники, производства и техники определяет образ современного общества. Важнейшей характерной чертой современного общества является то, что во всех его сферах заметна глобализация. Глобализация сама по себе требует быстрого движения, немедленного получения необходимой информации, ее обработки и эффективного применения на практике. Таким образом, только те кадры, которые хорошо разбираются в своей области, обладают высоким уровнем профессиональной квалификации, имеют богатый опыт и навыки. Поэтому в процессе подготовки кадров в высших учебных заведениях целесообразно учитывать данное требование периода.

Ключевые слова: образование, инновации, эффективность обучения, иностранный язык, грамматика, педагогическое мастерство.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan was recognized as an important direction of the reform carried out to improve the system of continuing education from the technologization of the educational process. The effectiveness of this process was ensured by the active use of modern educational technologies by teachers in educational practice, as well as awareness of modern technologies used in the practice of education of developed foreign countries on the basis of the following conditions.

For over the years of independence the Republic of Uzbekistan has carried out fundamental, structural and substantive reforms that have encompassed all levels of education system and its components, which were aimed at ensuring its compliance with the long-term objectives and interests of the country, modern requirements, as well as international standards. The appropriate legal framework reforming this sector was created, which defined as a priority the growth of investment, as well as the investments in human capital, training of educated and intellectually developed generation, which is the crucial asset and a decisive force in the achievement of democratic development, modernization and renewal, ensuring stable and sustainable growth of the economy.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

One of the culminating problem while creating the Democratic society is the change of human's education and thinking. The creation of new type of thinking, will become the principal factor of development which is based on the directions democratic society of the person's place and understanding the role in today's progress. Human is a main wealth in every nation. It can be concluded from this, the primary way of improving nation's wealth and power is to increase the each person's own creative skills. Nowadays the amount of money which are spent on education are just not simple expenses, probably they are considered as investments which bring economical income in a fast rate.

Innovation - is theoretically grounded, focused and practice - oriented innovation. The objectives of the innovative education are:

- Ensuring a high level of intellectual and personal and spiritual development of the student;
- Creation of conditions for mastering the skills they scientific way of thinking;
- Teaching methodology innovations in socio-economic and professional spheres.

Nowadays required to prepare a new professional quality, society needs not just a competent worker, and the expert, capable to self-oriented creative approach to business, with high culture of thinking, multilateral development people.

Many teachers of special subjects now ask, what should be a lesson for modern students with the knowledge of the maximum of what they are given.

We need to teach students how to learn for life, and for that the teacher must be capable of continuous updating of techniques to work with the new generation, to fit in a constantly changing environment, encourage students in their creative approach to the subject, using a variety of non-traditional forms and methods of teaching , innovative technologies.

Particular emphasis is placed on student-oriented technologies - cooperative learning, project-based learning, technology individualization and differentiation, multilevel training. Individualization technology is widely used in conducting training courses with course design, graduation design. Students' progress in the protection course or research projects show performance. Collective learning technology is used during the lessons in the form of workshops, talks, discussions, dialogues as a result of which is the solution of the problem situation to a student, for example, on the railways.

Training is carried out in co-operation during the laboratory and practical works on disciplines special cycle.

Learning is based on binary Stepping organization of cognitive and practical activities of students.

These lessons are lively, emotionally, in an atmosphere of high activity of students and cover material more than one discipline.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Under the prism of innovative technologies change the system checks the students in the knowledge of specialized disciplines. Modern methods of measuring the level of training of students, focused on the use of computer technology (computer testing), and fully meet the realities of the present, provide fundamentally new opportunities, increase the effectiveness of the teacher. A significant advantage of these technologies is that they provide new opportunities and student. Student of the object of study is transformed into a subject of study, consciously involved in the learning process and make their own decisions associated with it. Forte computer test control of knowledge is the ability to capture in the process of testing a large amount of material, and thus

get a really broad view of knowledge of the student test that allows you to significantly increase the objectivity, the detail and accuracy of the estimation results of the learning process.

Conducting lessons of special subjects using video, computer presentations - is a powerful incentive to learn. Through these lessons the students become active mental processes: perception, attention, memory, thinking; much more active and quicker arousal of cognitive interest. Information technologies provide information in various forms and thus make the learning process more effective. Saving the time required studying a particular material, the average is 30%, and acquired knowledge stored in the memory is much longer. Thus, the use of ICT in conjunction with the right technology training and create the necessary level of quality of education, variation, differentiation and individualization of learning.

In this regard, the following conclusions and highlight a number of advantages such a lesson in comparison with the ordinary:

- Improves the absorption of new material, as a result of the predominance of Visual thinking students easily perceive the information thus supplied;
- In the course of the students formed spatial and logical thinking;
- Naturally achieved by optimization of the pace of work of students;
- It is possible with the help of computer animation in the classroom to create a problematic situation, resulting in a lesson assumes the character of educational games, and most of the students increases the motivation of educational activity.

Integration of conventional lessons with a computer allows the teacher to shift part of their work on a PC, while making the learning process more interesting, diverse and intense. In particular, it is faster recording process definitions, objectives, and other important parts of the material, because the teacher does not have to repeat the text several times (he brought it to the screen), the student does not have to wait until it is again required him to fragment.

All this shows that the lesson using computer presentations has a higher efficiency compared to a conventional lesson.

The essence of innovative technologies aimed at the formation of skills is precisely to ensure that the students of these problems, in the solution of which they have mastered the techniques of activity.

CONCLUSION

All of the above leads to the conclusion that the major features innovative learning can be considered:

- Intensive development of the individual student and teacher;
- Democratization of their joint activity and communication;
- Humanization of the educational process;
- Focus on creative teaching and active learning, student initiative in forming themselves as future professionals;
- Modernization of the means, methods, technologies and facilities of learning, contributing to the formation of innovative thinking of the future professional.

In conclusion we can say applying innovation technologies are the main factor of the development of the country. We think that every citizen must be initiative and active in accelerating the process of applying innovation technologies.

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